

Primary Pleural Myxoid Liposarcoma Mimicking Pleural Effusion in a COVID-19-Positive Patient

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Introduction

Liposarcoma is a malignant mesenchymal tumor that accounts for 15% to 20% of all malignant mesenchymal tumors. Liposarcoma most commonly affects the lower extremities or the retroperitoneum. An intrathoracic origin is unusual, and most liposarcomas in the thoracic region develop in the mediastinum. The most prevalent kind of primary pleural liposarcoma (PPL) is the myxoid variety. Only a few cases of primary pleural liposarcoma have been reported worldwide. To our knowledge, this is the first reported case from the Sultanate of Oman.

Case Presentation

A 24-year-old male presented with a two-week history of shortness of breath and left-sided pleuritic chest pain, with productive cough but no fever or hemoptysis. He was otherwise healthy and tested positive for COVID-19. Chest X-ray showed a large left-sided opacity with mediastinal shift, and CT revealed a massive pleural collection with septations compressing the heart and great vessels. An intercostal chest drain yielded minimal output, and pleural fluid was negative for malignancy. On referral, he developed signs of cardiac tamponade and hemodynamic compromise. Imaging then suggested a low-density mass rather than fluid, prompting urgent left posterolateral thoracotomy. A large gelatinous mass occupying the pleural space and encasing mediastinal structures was excised (R2 resection). Histopathology confirmed primary pleural myxoid liposarcoma. Chemotherapy was initiated due to unresectable disease, but rapid progression was observed on follow-up imaging. Management was shifted to palliative care, and the patient died four months later.

Conclusion

Primary pleural myxoid liposarcoma is a rare thoracic malignancy that may present late with compressive symptoms and can mimic pleural fluid collections on imaging. Early recognition is essential, but prognosis may remain poor when complete surgical resection is not feasible.

Keywords

mediastinal shift, thoracotomy, myxoid liposarcoma, primary liposarcoma, covid-19